

Bias is in the Eye of the Beholder: How Users Understand Search Engine Bias and How It Affects Trust in Search Results

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1. Introduction

By filtering and ranking information, search engines such as Google or Bing play a crucial role in shaping user information diets. Research shows that users trust these platforms and tend to rely heavily on their ranking by selecting the top results (Schultheiß and Lewandowski, 2023; Häußler, 2023; Pan et al., 2007). Yet, similar to other algorithmic systems, it is well documented that search results are prone to various forms of (social) bias. For instance, studies show that search engines tend to systematically underrepresent women and non-white people, especially in image search (Guilbeault et al., 2024; Rohrbach, Makhortykh, and Sydorova, 2024). Such biases can influence how individuals perceive social reality, contributing to the reinforcement of stereotypes or unequal representation (Noble 2018).

While there is a growing body of literature on systematic distortions in search engine results, substantially less research has been done on how users perceive different forms of search bias and how these perceptions shape their information-seeking behavior. Some studies examined a general understanding of algorithmic bias (e.g., Mowshowitz and Kawaguchi, 2005; Goldman, 2008; Lewandowski, 2015; Rader and Gray, 2015), however, less is known about the specific types of bias that users themselves identify (e.g. Han et al., 2021). Yet, such perception is crucial for determining the extent to which users trust search engines and view information obtained through them as credible. For instance, Shin (2020) demonstrates that the perceived fairness of search algorithms significantly impacts user trust. Depending on their awareness and understanding of bias, individuals may be more or less likely to use search engines, which can have a direct effect on how informed they are about various political issues and, consequently, what political decisions they make.

This study builds on the existing research in two ways. First, it looks at how the perception of search bias in Switzerland, a direct democracy which is particularly reliant on the political participation of citizens and their awareness of current political issues, connects to a broad set of public values (e.g., fairness, equality, diversity) and anti-values (e.g., non-transparency, discrimination, and manipulativeness). Second, it explores how individual characteristics of search engine users (e.g., political interest and efficacy, search engine preferences, education level, and digital literacy skills) affect their perceptions of bias and trust in politics-related search engine results. To achieve these aims, the study uses data from two waves of a representative survey of Swiss citizens ($n = 1,100$ each) conducted in January and December of 2024, before two rounds of the national referendums. An open-ended question was used to capture users' understanding of search engine bias, with responses coded according to different categories of public values. Users' conceptualizations of bias were related, among

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other things, to the representation of different political perspectives, commercial interests, problems with the underlying algorithms, and susceptibility of platforms to external influence and manipulation.

This study provides new insights into the relationship between user awareness of search engine bias, trust in algorithmic curation of political information, and individual search behaviors. By examining how users navigate search engines, this research contributes to broader discussions on algorithmic literacy and trust in algorithm-driven platforms.

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